

In-source and in-trap formation of molecular ions in the actinide mass range at CERN-ISOLDE

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ABSTRACT

The use of radioactive molecules for fundamental physics research is a developing interdisciplinary field limited dominantly by their scarce availability. In this work, radioactive molecular ion beams containing actinide nuclei extracted from uranium carbide targets are produced via the Isotope Separation On-Line technique at the CERN-ISOLDE facility. Two methods of molecular beam production are studied: extraction of molecular ion beams from the ion source, and formation of molecular ions from the mass-separated ion beam in a gas-filled radio-frequency quadrupole ion trap. Ion currents of U^+ , UO_{1-3}^+ , UC_{1-3}^+ , UF_{1-4}^+ , $UF_{1,2}O_{1,2}^+$ are reported. Metastable tantalum and uranium fluoride molecular ions are identified. Formation of UO_{1-3}^+ , $U(OH)_{1-3}^+$, UC_{1-3}^+ , $UF_{1,2}O_{1,2}^+$ from mass-separated beams of U^+ , $UF_{1,2}^+$ with residual gas is observed in the ion trap. The effect of trapping time on molecular formation is presented.

1. Introduction

There is interdisciplinary interest in radioactive molecules bridging fields of molecular physics, atomic physics and nuclear physics, as well as physics beyond the standard model [1]. Experimental research possibilities with many radioactive molecules are currently constrained by their limited production. This is particularly the case for radioactive molecules containing an actinide element. Only actinides in the decay chains of primordial ^{232}Th and $^{235,238}\text{U}$ are available in macroscopic quantities in nature. All others must be produced artificially.

The Isotope Separation On-Line (ISOL) method allows production of a wide range of radioactive nuclides across the nuclear chart through reactions induced by the impact of an accelerated particle beam hitting a thick target. The ISOLDE facility at CERN [2] uses 1.4-GeV protons accelerated by CERN's Proton Synchrotron Booster (PSB) and can employ a variety of target and ion source systems. Once created, the reaction products must diffuse out of the target material and effuse to the ion source, where they are ionized and extracted as a beam of charged particles. For refractory species, forming volatile compounds has been employed as a technique to improve extraction from the target

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Fig. 4. Rates of ion beams from a tungsten surface ion source recorded on a Faraday Cup after mass separation from the ISOLDE separator magnets shown in logarithmic scale. (a), (b), (c): as a function of ion-source temperature for a target temperature of 1578 °C. (d) (e) (f): rates as a function of target temperature for an ion source temperature of 2230 °C. (c) and (f): rates of fragment ions measured on the apparent mass corresponding to the indicated dissociation of metastable molecular ions.

UO_2 (7.773(145) eV) [15] suggest that some dissociation of neutral and singly-charged oxides should occur within the FEBIAD ion source.

3.2. Metastable molecular ions

In mass spectrometry, the term ‘metastable’ is used to describe molecular ions possessing sufficient excess energy to fragment in the field-free region after leaving the ion source [16]. Upon fragmentation, the fragment ions retain a fraction of the kinetic energy of the extracted precursor ion. This causes fragment ions to pass through the mass separator magnetic field with an apparent mass m^* corresponding to [16]

$$m^* = \frac{m_f^2}{m_p} \quad (1)$$

where m_f represents the mass of the fragment ion and m_p represents the mass of the precursor metastable molecular ion. Fragment ions and their precursors were identified from the apparent mass and studied as a function of the target and surface ion source temperatures (Fig. 4). Increasing the ion source temperature significantly increased the fragment ion intensity, suggesting that at high temperatures, the molecules are more likely to have sufficient excess energy to reach the metastable states that fragment after extraction. Fragment molecules are indicated where observed in Fig. 3. Rates of U^+ , $\text{UF}_{1,2,3}^+$ and UF_xO_y^+ also increase with ion source temperature as surface ionization efficiency increases. This increase could also partially result from increased molecular fragmentation into ionic species occurring in the ion source.

4. In-trap molecular formation

To study in-trap molecular formation, the ISOLTRAP RFQ-cb was employed with a buffer gas (here He at up to 10^{-5} mbar measured within 1 m of the injection) to cool and bunch the ions. Mass-separated beams ionized using each of the studied ion sources were sent to the RFQ-cb for cooling and bunching. For studies of beam composition and in-trap molecular formation, a sample of the continuous ion beam was

Fig. 5. ToF spectrum of $A = 238$ mass-separated ion beams after cooling and bunching in the ISOLTRAP RFQ-cb, then trapping for 2000 revolutions in the MR-ToF MS as calculated for ^{238}U . The status of the U resonant laser (on or off) is indicated. Vertical lines shown in the top panel indicate ToFs expected from offline calibrations. See text for further details.

taken into the RFQ-cb. Ions were confined in the RFQ-cb for a trapping time during which interaction occurred between the ions, the buffer gas and residual gas contamination. The ion bunch was then ejected from the RFQ-cb and the arrival times of ions in each shot were measured with respect to the ejection time. Identification was performed with the MR-ToF MS using expected ToF values extracted from a calibration using $^{85,87}\text{Rb}^+$, $^{133}\text{Cs}^+$ from the ISOLTRAP offline ion source [17], and online $^{238}\text{U}^+$ from ISOLDE. ToF spectra were accumulated over a number of shots as seen in Figs. 5, 6, and 7.

The atomic uranium resonant laser ionization scheme in the ion source affected the count rates of uranium molecules (e.g. UO^+ and UOH^+ in Fig. 5) observed from the RFQ-cb ion trap. Combined with the mass-separation step of the separator magnets, this indicates that the molecules are formed from ions in the mass-separated U^+ beam rather than in the target or ion source. For U and Ta, ratios depend on the trapping time as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. In addition to atomic ions forming molecules, molecular ions mass-separated by ISOLDE (including UF^+ , UF_2^+ , TaF^+ , TaF_2^+) reacted with the residual gas or buffer-gas contaminants to form molecules by pickup of C, O, H and OH (Figs. 7,8) and in some cases (UF^+ , UF_2^+) were observed with higher charge states (UF^{2+} , UF_2^{2+}). To avoid detector saturation, attenuators were used to reduce the intensity of the ion beam injected into the RFQ-cb. This reduced absolute rates of in-trap formation and the formation efficiency relative to the ion beam intensity extracted from the ion source. Rates of molecular formation in the ion-trap represent ratios in the regime below space-charge limitations.

Notably, the in-trap UO_x formation showed an identical response to the storage time in the RFQ-cb before and after the addition of a liquid nitrogen cold trap to the buffer gas line, indicating that reaction products enter the ion trap through diffusion into the vacuum chamber rather than buffer gas injection.

5. Conclusions

For previously irradiated or oxidized targets, UO^+ and UO_2^+ sidebands are on the order of 10^5 ions s^{-1} at target temperatures above 1600 °C. Without further addition of oxygen, the intensity of these contaminants will decrease over time, with the UO_2^+ sideband depleting first, followed by the UO^+ sideband. At nominal target temperatures (2000 °C) and above, UC^+ , UC_2^+ can similarly reach rates of 10^4 ions s^{-1} or more. Fragments formed from the dissociation of metastable U and Ta fluorides arrive as additional non-isobaric contaminants in mass-separated beams. Fragment ions and their precursor ions can be identified using their apparent mass (Eq. (1)) and anticipated for a given mass-to-charge ratio with the rates presented here. We present some representative rates of molecular ions extracted from different ion

To form molecules that may not be stable at high temperatures, molecular formation in the RFQ ion trap is presented as a possible approach. Formation of oxides, carbides, and hydroxides from the mass-separated atomic and molecular ion beams occurs in the ISOLTRAP RFQ-cb in the presence of residual gases. Trapping time is shown to be a parameter influencing the formation of molecules in the ion trap. The molecular formation reported here in the ISOLTRAP RFQ-cb may have implications for other RFQ-cb ion traps used in beam preparation (e.g. the ISOLDE cooler ISCOOL [2]) which require further investigations.

These studies combined characterize the composition of beams heavier than the target material and provide information on the process of creating molecular actinide beams in targets and in ion traps.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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